

Collaboration for Relieving Poverty, Social Development and Community Well-being in Maha Sarakham Province, Thailand

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: April 25, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: July 05, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Community, Collaboration, Poverty, Social Development, PAR, Well-being</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5071240</p>	<p><i>The community development project with a budget of 2,800,000 Baht successfully created a collaboration model to relieve poverty, social development, and community well-being. The local sub-district administrative organization (SAO) and the Bank for Agriculture and Agricultural Cooperatives (BAAC) were vital partners in the project and the participants from 175 households. Participatory Action Research (PAR) processes were applied 1) field trip to model villages, 2) feasibility analysis, 3) studying the current problems, 4) data analysis, 5) participatory planning, 6) action planning, 7) potential development, 8) follow-up and evaluation, and 9) sharing knowledge. Action learning and cycles of reflection increased the action and awareness of participants. The collaborative model transformed participants into co-researchers and elevating awareness and self-initiation. The project was also successful in creating a community database, learning process, and knowledge management, and created an association and continuity for social development. Participants overall were satisfied at a "Very Good" level. Participants initiated comprehensive agricultural practices, created new commercial groups, used cost-saving measures, learned proper accounting practices, and applied sufficiency economy philosophy.</i></p>

Introduction

Sufficiency economy philosophy is an important development principle of King Rama 9. It is a guidance standpoint and aims for Thai society to be a strong society, self-reliant and balanced in 3 areas, which include, a quality society, a prudent and learning society, and a society in harmony and compassion towards one another. Therefore, practical implementations of the principle, theory, and philosophy should lead to the formulation of policies, objectives, real practices, improvements, and development of organizations, departments, groups, communities, and all participants. This is in congruence with the speech by King Rama 9, at the Kasetsart University graduation ceremony on 18 April 1960. He pointed out the importance of farmers to the national economy. *"The economy of Thailand depends largely on farmers. Therefore, you must always remember this great essence. And help restore the country's agriculture to progress quickly."* This is also consistent with the speech given to graduates from Khon Kaen University on December 20, 1973, *"For national development, it is necessary to put primary importance on the fundamental structure, that is, the sufficiency livelihood of the majority of the people first. By using methods and equipment that are economical but accurate under the principles. Once the basic foundation is stable, then gradually build up prosperity and expand the economic base in the future."* (Chantarasombat, 2009: 117-119).

Research and community development projects all begin with the appointment of a committee. But collaboration and communication are the driving force in the success of community development. The cooperation and teamwork between official and unofficial leaders at the village level and sub-district level to solve community problems by applying the philosophy of sufficiency economy are still insignificant. This might be because there is no mechanism for knowledge management to organize groups in the community or the lack of leadership or low self-awareness. This is also true at the sub-district level. Sub-district health development projects lack efficiency due to the lack of collaboration and awareness between the local administrative office, and community organizations. Community development requires real action and practical solutions. Government and private sectors must increase their cooperation and efforts to solve poverty and community development. This will enable farmers in Maha Sarakham province with the ability to efficiently manage agricultural production, create a network of cooperation within the province, build a healthy community, and community well-being through sufficiency economy.

The researchers proposed a community development project in collaboration with the Bank for Agriculture and Agricultural Cooperatives (BAAC), Maha Sarakham, Mahasarakham University, community schools, indigenous knowledge groups, and the sub-district administration organization utilizing Participatory action research (PAR) and action learning activities to create a cooperation model for poverty relief, social

development and well-being for the communities in Maha Sarakham Province. The 1st phase of the project proposal was approved with a budget of 350,000 Baht and was conducted from March 2011 – February 2012.

BACKGROUND

Examples from the study of indigenous knowledge and the Sufficiency Economy Learning Center of Mr. Chandi Pratumapa, Chum Phuang District, Nakhon Ratchasima Province. Mr. Chandi focuses on making the most use of the 23 rai of land, resulting in innovative solutions to poverty. He contributes to his success to knowledge management through Action learning that provides real-world results. Another example is the effort of Phra Maha Supab, the Abbot of Wat Pa Na Khum Monastery, and the administrator of The Farmer Learning Center for Self-Reliance. The abbot developed the concept of one rai without poverty with real-world results and focused on creating a real body of knowledge from practice. The success of the center was measured through success indicators of the people in the focus group. Participating farmers who wanted to clear their debts began the participatory process of reviewing income-expenses accounts and applied knowledge management which enabled farmers to solve the problem by themselves at the family level through learning by doing. The knowledge and process can be transferred to interested farmers that have high expectations.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

1. What is the appropriate solution to poverty relief in a community?
2. How can a community database be used in making policies in local community development?
3. Can an integrated action for poverty relief lead to collaboration and real action?

RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

1. To create a collaboration mechanism for community participants to solve poverty, create social development and well-being that is appropriate for the locality.
2. To develop a community-based database system to formulate development policy for different community levels.
3. To create a learning process and knowledge management to solve economic, social, and health problems.
4. Create an association and continuity for social development.

RESEARCH SIGNIFICANCE

1. The result of the research can create an appropriate cooperative working model for provincial administrations to solve poverty and efficiently manage the agricultural system of farmers.
2. The research results can create a learning network and knowledge management model to solve poverty and efficient management of the agricultural system of farmers that can be extended across communities, sub-districts, provinces, and regional networks.

METHODOLOGY

The research area included 6 districts, 6 sub-districts, and 12 villages of Maha Sarakham Province. The area was purposively sampled by using the “target village readiness database” of the Bank for Agriculture and Agricultural Cooperatives (BAAC), Maha Sarakham Province. Six districts were randomly selected, namely Wapi Pathum District, Na Dun District, Na Chueak District, Kantharawichai District, Kudrang District, Chuen Rak District. The researchers and selected district administrators held a meeting with sub-district administrators to solicit which sub-district would like to volunteer for the research. Six sub-districts, one from each district chose to participate which are 1) Na Kha sub-district, Wapi Pathum district 2) Phra That sub-district, Na Dun district 3) Nong Pho sub-district, Na Chueak district, 4) Khwao Yai sub-district, Kantharawichai district, 5) Loeng Faek sub-district, Kut Rang district 6) Lao Dok Mai sub-district, Chuen Chom District. The focus group consists of 175 households from 12 villages namely Ban Bua Kaew (Village No. 3 and 4, Kut Rang District), Ban Nong Bueng (Village No. 3 and 8, Na Chueak District), Ban Dong Noi (Moo 4 and 5, Na Dun District), Ban Ton Mu (Village No. 8 Wapi Pathum District), Ban Wang Chan (Village No. 4 Kantharawichai District), Ban Wang Mai (Village No. 13 Kantharawichai District), Ban Wang Nuea (Village No. 16 Kantharawichai District), Ban Hin Poon (Village No. 17), and Ban Nong Khu (Village No. 6, Chuen Chom District)

Action Learning and PAR processes are used extensively in the research. The PAR processes were divided into 9 processes 1) field trip to model villages, 2) feasibility analysis, 3) study the current problems, conditions, and needs of the target community, 4) data analysis, 5) participatory planning, 6) plan of action and adjustments, 7) potential development and upgrading the body of knowledge, 8) follow-up and evaluation, and 9) sharing the gained knowledge with others. The research instruments include household account books, life quality development plans, administrative operational manuals, community development plans, manual for poverty relief, and community well-being. Data collection used evaluation forms and success indicators.

Statistics to measure the research indicators include frequency, percentage mean, and standard deviation recommended by Srisa-ard(2002:101 – 103).

RESULT

Cooperation Mechanism

Conceptual Framework:Project management, Action Learning and PAR were utilized to design and construct a community development model to solve poverty, create social development and create community well-being in Maha Sarakham Province. This can be achieved by adapting PAR processes demonstrated by Chantarasombat (2008: 15) which included 7 steps 1) team preparation, 2) studying the current situations, problems. 3) the needs of the project 4) participatory planning, 5) implementing the plan and improving the process, 6) Conclusion and 7) the exchange of knowledge. (figure 1)

The researchers improved PAR process for poverty relief, create social development and well-being with 9 processes namely 1) field trip to model villages, 2) feasibility analysis, 3) study the current problems, conditions, and needs of the target community, 4) data analysis, 5) participatory planning, 6) plan of action and adjustments, 7) potential development and upgrading the body of knowledge, 8) follow-up and evaluation, and 9) sharing the gained knowledge with others. (figure 2)

Action learning activities encouraged farmers to participate. The 5 action learning activities were divided into 5 stages, these include 1) goal setting, 2) planning, 3) implementation plan, improvements, and adjustments, 4) reflections, and 5) sharing the knowledge to participants, communities, sub-districts, districts, and provinces. (Chantarasombat, 2009: 424-427).

Stage 1 Goal Setting (March-May 2011):The researchers approached the community at the village level, sub-district, district, and provincial levels to conduct preliminary research. The researchers and participants worked together as a team to study, observe, and analyze the source of poverty and social-economic factors in the target communities. Designing a community model to solve poverty, create social development, and create well-being utilized PAR. Based on the analyzed data and objectives, the final research tools and instruments before implementation was complete after cycles of reflection and expert reviews. The research tools included a community development model, implementation plan, household accounting book for incomes and expenses, manual for developing well-being, brochures, posters for publicizing the project, learning activities, work assignments, mechanisms, evaluation criteria, success indicators, database, webpage, documentation, and a manual for the participants.

Stage 2 Planning (March-July 2011): This stage involved analyzing income data and expenses models of households. Researchers used a tree chart diagram to analyze the internal and external factors. The researchers also agreed and designed a life quality plan for each household and a community development plan that involves at least creating one development center for each village. The community learning center was divided into selected occupational groups for each village. Learning by doing activities were designed to match the need of the target community. Schedule activities, collaboration, resources, and budget requirements were estimated and reviewed by experts before submitting it to the experts for review and final approval.

Stage 3 PAR Planning (June-September 2011):The concluded implementation plans, community well-being maps, community master plan, supporting brochures, and action learning activities were presented to the provincial administration for approval. A Memorandum Understanding (MOU) was signed by all participants. Research staff and participants were trained in proper household accounting practices and how to record their incomes and expenditures.

Figure 2. Action Learning (Chalard Chantarasombat,2008: 224)

Step 4 Reflections (October-December 2011):Self-reflection is the major factor used in the conceptual framework of the research. The action learning activities developed potentials and a body of knowledge through training while reflection generated awareness. The participants' awareness in keeping household accounts and the realization of their income, debts, and needed investments were decisive in the participants' collaboration and the success of the research. Self-awareness led participants at Nakha sub-district to make changes from purchasing rice seeds and seedlings to produce and grow their own. Lao Dok Mai participants embraced examples of comprehensive agriculture production by plowing over the rice stalks and enriching the soil. Participants at Phra That sub-district made purchases of consumables in bulk.

Stage 5 Sharing (January-February 2012):Participants shared their knowledge with academics, administrators from the sub-districts, districts, and from the provincial office. Collaboration and competition lead to self-development and efficient development of the community. The summary and evaluation as a team improved the learning process and the development model. Administrators were able to gain insight into practical solutions that they can incorporate for future development projects in their community. Participation by the farmers, officials from the administrative offices, the hospital, and from the BAAC created trust, unity, and recognition.

Community Database

Researchers stored the research data and statistical records at each community level in a database system. Research participants and administrative offices had full access to the information in the database which can be accessed through the website of the project. The information was collected through observation forms, interview forms, documents, household accounting records, lists of expenditures, and debts. Analyzing the data according to the location of communities provided the researchers with the facts and details for designing a development plan and solution to poverty relief, creating social development and well-being. The community database included a record-keeping of the operations and implementation of facts and figures of the project. The recorded information came from the research instruments, forms, and notes of participants and researchers in each community. The data is stored in many forms, including hard copy documents, electronic files, accounting programs, and household accounting records. The data was entered into the project's website "<https://health.drchalard.com>". With statistics and information on income, expenditure, community wellness maps, evaluation results before the development and after the development.

The data in the database was analyzed and synthesized to formulate policies and plans in the form of social and health quality development plans, community master plans, poverty relief pilot plans, family

accounting guidelines and liabilities model, and project guideline references. The results of the post-development assessments are also included in the database so that participants can post their views and opinions. The community database was essential in providing good communication and statistics between community groups, administrative offices, project partners, and the research team. The database connected the participants at all levels, communities, sub-districts, districts, and provinces.

The poverty relief plan of every community was included in the 3-year local development plan of the sub-district administrative organizations (SAO). The poverty relief, social development, and well-being plans and results were also included in the 2012 provincial expenditure budget. Totalling 350,000 baht, consisting of 50,000 Baht's was allocated for Loeng Faek sub-district, 50,000 Baht's for Nong Pho sub-district, 50,000 baht's for Phra That Noi sub-district, 100,000 Baht's for Nakha sub-district, and 100,000 Baht's for Lao Dok Mai sub-district.

Learning Process and Knowledge Management

The researchers followed up progress and evaluated the learning process and efficiency of the PAR through meetings and discussions hosted by the BAAC. Participants from all sub-districts exchanged their experiences and ideas. They worked together as a team to find solutions to the different challenges and developments in their communities. The exchange of knowledge and action learning enabled the participants to better understand the current situations and plan an effective solution. Systematically following the PAR and research guidelines increased the efficiency, which was measured by the post-development and pre-development indicators in Table 1.

Table 1. Result of Collaboration for Poverty Relief, Social Development, and Well-being Mahasarakham Province. (Period 1) (6 Villages, Mahasarakham Province)

Indicator	Comparison	Households	(\bar{x})	(SD)	t	Sig
Overall Project (6 Villages)	After	174	3.686	0.502	9.465	.000**
	Before	174	2.999	.839		

Table 2. Poverty Relief

Indicator	Comparison	Households	(\bar{x})	(SD)	t	Sig
Overall Poverty Relief	After	175	3.53	0.621	10.049	.000**
	Before	175	2.72	0.903		
Reduce Expenses	After	175	3.48	0.707	9.017	.000**
	Before	175	2.71	0.893		
Increase revenue in household	After	175	3.47	0.698	8.219	.000**
	Before	175	2.68	1.045		
Extend the opportunity of Increase revenue and Productivity in household	After	175	3.53	0.732	6.961	.000**
	Before	175	2.79	1.173		

*Sig. .05

**Sig. .01

Table 3. Social Development

Indicator	Comparison	Households	(\bar{x})	(SD)	t	Sig
Overall Social Development	After	175	3.74	0.543	6.109	.000**
	Before	175	3.29	0.853		
HumanResourcedevelopment	After	175	4.02	0.571	12.017	.000**
	Before	175	2.96	1.109		
Religion Culture Tradition	After	175	4.02	0.571	3.729	.000**
	Before	175	3.73	0.904		
Learning in household	After	175	3.37	0.710	7.000	.000**
	Before	175	2.71	1.002		

*Sig.. 05

**Sig.. 01

Table 4. Well-Being Development

Indicator	Comparison	Households	(\bar{x})	(SD)	t	Sig
Overall Well-being	After	175	3.76	0.537	4.577	.000**
	Before	175	3.39	1.016		
Personal Well-being	After	175	3.70	0.613	6.700	.000**
	Before	175	3.08	1.088		
Environmenthealth	After	175	3.81	0.567	5.648	.000**
	Before	175	3.33	1.047		

*Sig.. 05

**Sig.. 01

Action learning activities and training courses on vocational skills, finance, proper accounting practices, and sufficiency economy were necessary for creating a collaborative mechanism to solve poverty, create social development and well-being. Loeng Faek, Nong Pho, Phra That, and Nakha sub-districts trained at

Mr. Sawaeng Manolai's learning center in Dong Khang Noi sub-district, Kaset Wisai district, Roi Et province. Khwao Yai sub-district participants, trained in making fish feed at the "Rai Zero" Shrimp Federation in Yang Talat district, Kalasin province, and at the "Don Man Village Learning Center" in Kham Riang sub-district, Kantharawichai district, Maha Sarakham province. Lao Dokmai sub-district participants trained at Don Daeng sub-district in Borabue district and Talad Mueng sub-district in Na Chueak district. Both centers provided vocational skills in making animal feeds and comprehensive farming skills.

Loeng Faek Sub-district: Researchers and participants implemented an accounting and economic development plan. Each participant's household worked as a team to strictly record all financial gains and expenditures with guidance and support of the research team. Families were provided with training, and practices in proper bookkeeping by the BAAC. Seven households grew plant pots and vegetable gardens to create additional income and for personal consumption. Every household is a member of the Government Savings bank. Researchers collaborated with the participants to create a biofertilizer production group, which lowered the cost of expenditures of the families during the agricultural season.

Nong Pho Sub-district: A financial plan and financial advice provided the participants and each household to reduce costs and control their finances. Planting sheds and gardens created supplemental income and savings for each household. Participants also gained knowledge and exchanged experiences with cottage industries outside of their community through a field trip arranged by the research. Action learning activities include environmental conservation in their community and planting trees at the forest monastery.

Phra That Sub-district: Three Sufficiency Economy Philosophy learning centers were established in the community for the 62 participating households. The financial plans created for each of the families was effective, reducing unnecessary expenses. New jobs were created and the participants created 9 career network groups in their community. The income and trade benefits extended to the community and neighboring villages. Environmental conservation at Phra That sub-district included agricultural campaigns in plowing techniques, sewing the land, and turning over rice stocks reducing the dependency on purchased fertilizer and revitalized the soil. The increased agricultural production led to increasing commerce between other communities and raised the livelihood of the participating families. The researchers coordinated with Nadun district hospital and community healthcare volunteers to conduct health surveys, organize healthy living workshops and diabetic treatments in the community. Nadun hospital also makes regular visits to the sub-district every 3 months to provide healthcare services and well-being checkups.

Nakha Sub-district: There is a total of 12 sufficiency economy learning households in the community and one central learning center in the village. Similar financial training and planning were introduced in the sub-district and were successful in lower the expenses and poverty of the households. A rubber tree planting network created jobs and incomes from the examples and guidance of the community's entrepreneur, Mr. Na Sudphan. The participants followed his example and implemented his technique in growing and selling natural rubber from 2 rai (2x 1,600 square meters) of land. The participants in Nakha benefited from renewed friendships and trust in working as a team and reinstating traditional methods of communal rice harvesting to help each other.

Khwao Yai Sub-district: The researchers successfully established one central learning center in every village. Researchers and participants together nominated a group within their community to review and give financial advice to participating households. The group successfully help participants to reduce costs and increase their income. Freshwater fish cage aquaculture and culturing channel apple snails provided participants with supplementary income. Participants lowered the costs for fish food by culturing channeled apple snails, which was crushed with a feed grinder provided by the research project. Khwao Yai participants were also able to provide relief food and donate to flood victims in the community. They also donated rice seeds and rice seedlings. The charitable donations were made possible because of the extra incomes and cost-saving measures from the project. The group also expanded into mushroom culture creating a new source of income for families.

Lao Dok Mai sub-district: Participants were mostly concerned with the high costs of foods, education, the high investment in rice farming, pig farming, and animal feeds. The research group arranged field trips to see examples of comprehensive agriculture, farms, and examples of a sufficiency economy. The gained knowledge from exchanging experiences with other farmers improved the incomes of the participants. Participants implemented cost-cutting measures and techniques, but the cost of education remained the same. Commercial training and BAAC financial consultants helped the participants to get better margins from the community's bag sewing venture (bag sewn from fertilizer sacks).

Association and Continuity to Social Development

The community development project was effective because the researchers received full support from all the participants in the project. The governor supported the researchers and the project by officially issuing Maha Sarakham provincial order number 918/2011. The official order gave the research team authority to research, ensuring the full cooperation from sub-district, district, and provincial administrative offices. At the

community level, at least 15 public healthcare volunteers were participating in each village. The administrators and community leaders provided the research team assistance and supporting staff. Local schools provided personnel support and academic advisors in recording household accounting data and analysis. Hospitals provided healthcare training and hosted meetings and focus groups. The BAAC provided academic knowledge on proper accounting practices and financial support for the research. They also hosted learning activities, accounting seminars, and was the projects' financial advisor. The office of Provincial Community Development and the office of Provincial Social Development supported the research by allocating staff to work with the research team. The provincial auditors provided the publication of accounting books. The office of Commerce funded the purchase of a feed grinder for the project at the Khwao Yai sub-district. The Institute for Higher Education at Mahasarakham University coordinated the research efforts. All participants signed a memorandum of understanding, agreement, and commitments at the start of the research. Participatory planning and analysis of the plans relied on the collaboration mechanism of all the participants involved in the project. This resulted in a collaborative network which used many tools such as household account records, community well-being map, and a community master plan. This approach led to the creation of integrated operations, the expenditures were within the budget and proper allocation of shared resources between the participants.

The research applied action learning and PAR to create development plans and improved it with cycles of reflection and improvements. The result is a set of refined activities to solve real-world problems. The research team encouraged and promoted participants to work in groups at various levels in the target community. The participants changed their role from being the subjects of the research to becoming co-researchers through PAR. The different views and inputs that the participants contributed to the project, enhanced the efficiency of the implementation plan. The instruments and mechanisms constructed by the researchers were flexible and were corrected when needed. The ability to customize activities through participatory action planning encourages the working staff at the target communities to meet objectives and take action when it was needed. The self-awareness and ability to initiate action on their own was demonstrated by the participants in Khwao Yai sub-district and Nong Pho sub-district. The participants started mushroom culture immediately after their field trip. The initial plan was to wait for the budget release from the provincial administrative office, but participants were confident and familiar with mushrooms because they purchased them in large quantities every day from outside the community. The raw materials required for mushroom culture were already available in their community. Participants in both villages raised the necessary funds on their own to start their cottage industry without waiting for the budget from the project to be dispersed.

Conclusions and reflection are integral parts of learning by doing. Developing the capabilities, the capacity of knowledge through action learning activities such as field trips to vocational training centers, knowledge management course, and follow-ups contributed to lowering the poverty levels in the community. The most effective activity was encouraging and promoting the participating families to strictly record their expenditures and incomes. When the statistical numbers were summarized, the participants will have a definitive portrayal of their financial portfolio. The awareness in their financial status prompted participants to take action which was encouraged by the collaboration of participants. The awareness of the importance of agriculture was also realized leading them to find methods to lower the costs of agricultural expenditures. This was a profound revelation by participants and they embraced the sufficiency economy philosophy. The participants in Nakha created groups to produce rice seeds and rice seedlings instead of purchasing them. Lao Dok Mai participants chose to implement comprehensive agricultural methods which they experienced during the field trips. They started to sow the soil by plowing over rice stalks as supplementary fertilizer instead of using chemical fertilizers or burning like in the past. Participants in Phra That sub-district decided to buy goods and consumables in bulk instead of buying retail.

The exchange of ideas and experience occurred during meetings of the project. The participants presented their community's accomplishments to the group, their findings, and also their updates. Knowledge is also exchanged as participants learn from each other's experience and the exchange with academics, public administrators, from the BAAC, and healthcare officials. The gathering of ideas and results is competitive and this action learning experience is beneficial to creating initiative and awareness. The current status and problems of the community are also acknowledged by the administrative offices of each level. This will benefit the entire community and create a continuous and sustained development. It will also aid in future development policies by the provincial office.

DISCUSSION

Community development must always be supplemented with individual awareness. Using Participatory Action Research (PAR) and action learning to relieve poverty is consistent with views of the National Institute of Development Administration (2006: 114-117) which considers that poverty originates from within the individual. Individual poverty affects the family and their community. To find a solution to poverty, researchers and academics must create self-awareness from within the community. Individuals must know oneself, know their family, and know their community. Individuals must also identify the boundaries of poverty in

themselves, in their family and their community. Development policies and activities to relieve poverty must always include methods and mechanisms to create self-awareness, acknowledgment, and understanding of what poverty is to the individual participants. Having such knowledge will lead to the most direct and practical solution to relieving poverty.

Promoting and supporting cottage industries and community commercial groups in the project created new sources of income for individuals and families in Maha Sarakham. The training and field trips provided academic and vocational skills that the participants applied to lower costs and boost profit margins in agriculture and entrepreneurship. The development of skills and knowledge through training and exchange of experiences by using PAR is to gain experience, identification of new knowledge, analyzing the gained knowledge, planning and practice are an important process for participatory development. The strategy to relieve individual and family poverty is consistent with the findings of Boonyaratanasunthon & Phatanonthapatamadum (2007:253-254). Their assessment to relieving poverty emphasized on increasing incomes from micro-indicators such as increasing the GDP per head of physical micro-investment and infrastructure development.

The project's database provided statistical data before the development, during the development, and after the development. The implementation plan, activities, and indicators were constantly analyzed through a cycle of conclusion and reflection. Having the information in a database that could be accessed by all participants created clarity and a continuous PAR cycle. The participants themselves choose the most practical solution to relieve poverty in each community and are reflected in the conclusion and indicators throughout the PAR cycle. Poverty can be considered as a cycle of financial state that can change from being a "transient poor" to "chronic poor" and finally being "poorest". This means that poverty can be alleviated by developing or correcting the cycle of poverty.

The research team was informed of the project's status, important lessons, obstacles, and ongoing action plan through the essential PAR processes. These include process in surveying the current conditions, household account information, community health data, data analysis, participatory planning, implementation plans, monitoring plans, evaluation plans, knowledge capacity development, generating a new body of knowledge, conclusion of results, exchange of knowledge, training, and presentation performance of each community. PAR has been used in the development of knowledge management by academics such as Chantarasombat (2004: 21) which applied the PAR process in organizing and constructing a community master plan that begins an initial survey and data analysis that created guidelines for self-development. The process was aided by creating educational tools, action learning activities, learning by doing and collaboration mechanisms to create populist strategies that challenged the participant's interests and induced their cooperation.

Proper PAR consists of participating in the decision making, participating in the operations, and participating in the evaluation. But true PAR concerns participating in identifying the problems and their causes, participating in planning the activities, investing, and participation in the monitoring and evaluation of the results. He also goes to describe that there are different levels of participation which consist of decision-making, cooperation, and utilization. Kaeohawong (2000: 30-39) divides PAR processes into ladder steps. His 8 step PAR process includes treatment, explanations, information, discussion, expression of ideas, collaboration, empowerment, and supervision. The researchers choose to divide the PAR process into 9 processes namely 1) field trip to model villages, 2) feasibility analysis, 3) study the current problems, conditions, and needs of the target community, 4) data analysis, 5) participatory planning, 6) plan of action and adjustments, 7) potential development and upgrading the body of knowledge, 8) follow-up and evaluation, and 9) sharing the gained knowledge with others. PAR is a collection of action learning techniques combined to solve real-world problems. There are no limitations to how many processes or steps are definitive. The processes are constructed in collaboration with all participants and reviewed as a team to meet the objectives. Final approval should always come from expert reviews. Chantarasombat (2002: 30-39) recommends developing multi-dimensional indicators by using PAR which can effectively be applied to develop career groups, cottage industries, and the management of commercial entities. The researchers developed 73 indicators in collaboration with the participants, academic experts, and administrators. The indicators focused on the aspects of poverty relief, social development, and well-being in the community by using PAR. The success indicators were mutually agreed upon by all the participants and reviewed by the academic experts. Modifications, improvements to the activities, work assignments, and success indicators were done in collaboration between all parties.

Rammasoot (1997: 31) describes that PAR is efficient and extensively used as the conceptual framework, construction, and implementation in community development. While PAR processes can enhance the cooperation and understanding between participants and the administrative groups but researchers and academics must get full cooperation and approval from administrative offices before the project proposal. Community development projects rely heavily on local resources. Researchers must coordinate with local administrative agencies and offices at every level in the community. The cooperation and approval of the provincial office, district office, sub-district administrative organizations (SAO), and the Bank for Agriculture and Agricultural Cooperatives (BAAC) was essential for the success of the project. The provincial authorization to conduct the project enabled cooperation from the district and sub-district offices. The funding from the

BAAC provided the necessary expense to carry out the implementation, field trips, training, workshops, publication fees, and capital for funding community startups.

CONCLUSION

The 1st phase of the project in 2011 was successful. The local sub-district administrative organization (SAO) and the Bank for Agriculture and Agricultural Cooperatives (BAAC), were vital partners in the project. They contributed staff and financial support that enabled the researchers to implement the community development plan that connected communities, sub-districts, districts and the provincial office in a coordinated effort to relieve poverty, create social development and well-being in Maha Sarakham province. Professional advice and training at organized field trips were substantial and professional. Participants overall were satisfied at a "Very Good" level. Vocational training and academic courses on finance, accounting, and sufficiency economy created awareness and identified the need to relieve poverty, social development, and well-being. Each community is different and requires different solutions and actions. Participatory Action Research (PAR) and action learning created efficient communication between participants, created unity, created a new body of knowledge, and created competitiveness among individuals and groups.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Policy Recommendations

Local administrative organizations should make a community master plan that includes annual reviews and debates in the community. Sub-district administrators will benefit from creating a master plan which will aid administrators in future development projects. The master plan guidelines are capable of addressing current social issues and situations. A community master plan will enhance and support administrators' efforts and lead to concrete, practical solutions to social problems. Review mechanisms are essential in the assessment and improvement of the master plan before sharing it with others. The provincial development committee should implement the project as a pilot project for solving debts and poverty in the community. The project will generate continuous development and prosperity to communities in Maha Sarakham province. The Bank for Agriculture and Agricultural Cooperative should consider household accounts and records of the farmers in each area. The statistics and facts are beneficial for property loan guarantees for individuals and their families. One benefit of group discussions in the project is that a supplemental career is good for the livelihood of families in the community.

Poverty Relief

Researchers and project managers must participate and communicate with participants and establish excellent communication skills with the private and public sectors. Participants must conduct themselves with responsibility and diligently carry out the assigned tasks. Community collaboration is essential in poverty relief. Researchers and project managers must identify and try different techniques and choose the best instrument that is best suited for poverty relief in the target community. Each community is unique, and researchers should always keep their development plans and guidelines flexible and always consider improvements and adaptations. Participants should keep a monthly income and expense account. The monetary statistics will assist participants to plan for self-improvement in their finances and be an example in group activities in the development of social planning.

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